

Section
(Meta)data,
Terminology,
Provenance

Working Group
Research Software
Metadata

Working Group Charter

Research Software Metadata

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Name of the working group

Research Software Metadata

Acronym

section-metadata-wg-rsmeta

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Summary

Research software is commonly used in various disciplines to perform research and as a research object itself. Therefore, it is covered by multiple NFDI consortia. To fulfill the FAIR criteria for research software, it needs to be described with meaningful and interoperable metadata enhancing transparency, reproducibility, and reusability in research. While there exist some metadata schemes for research software, e.g., CodeMeta, they have some limitations, e.g., missing elements and missing semantic interoperability.

To address these issues, this working group aims to provide a comprehensive metadata vocabulary for research software, compatible with existing frameworks such as schema.org and CodeMeta. Also, the working group will support all NFDI consortia in applying the vocabulary as well as develop domain-specific extensions if needed.

Zusammenfassung

Forschungssoftware wird in vielen Bereichen der Wissenschaft zur Forschung genutzt und stellt teilweise selbst ein Forschungsobjekt dar. Viele NFDI-Konsortien decken Forschungssoftware als wichtiges Forschungsartefakt mit ab und wollen, dass Forschungssoftware in Zukunft die FAIR-Kriterien erfüllt, um die Transparenz, Reproduzierbarkeit und Wiederverwendbarkeit in software-basierter Forschung zu erhöhen. Damit Forschungssoftware die FAIR-Kriterien erfüllt, muss sie mit aussagekräftigen und interoperablen Metadaten beschrieben werden. Dafür werden entsprechende Metadaten schemata benötigt. Es gibt zwar einige Metadaten schemata für Forschungssoftware, z. B. CodeMeta, aber sie weisen einige Einschränkungen auf, z. B. fehlende Elemente und fehlende semantische Interoperabilität. Um diese Probleme zu beheben, hat sich diese Arbeitsgruppe zum Ziel gesetzt, ein umfassendes Metadaten vokabular für Forschungssoftware bereitzustellen, das mit bestehenden Standards wie schema.org und CodeMeta kompatibel ist. Damit wird die Arbeitsgruppe alle NFDI-Konsortien bei der Anwendung und Etablierung von Metadaten schemata für Forschungssoftware unterstützen, z. B. bei Entwicklung von bereichsspezifischen Erweiterungen.

1. Motivation

“Research software is created during the research process or for a research purpose”¹. It is commonly used in various disciplines to conduct research, e.g., to solve equations, simulate complex systems, analyze or transform data, and statistically test models (e.g., climate or meteorological models). Provenance and rich descriptions of research software are important to improve scientific transparency, reproducibility, and reusability. To enhance the FAIRness of research software^{2,3}, software metadata play an important role.³

To improve its interoperability, these metadata should be based on a common metadata vocabulary. *CodeMeta*⁴ is a community-driven metadata standard for research software based on the classes *SoftwareApplication* and *SoftwareSourceCode* of *schema.org*⁵. Various crosswalks to other metadata schemes already exist. *CodeMeta* contains multiple elements, some focusing on technical details like file size or supported operating systems, and others including administrative information like licenses. It supports the use of URIs for authors, contributors, and licenses. The content-specific metadata are limited to keywords. *CodeMeta* is trying to incorporate its definitions into *schema.org*.

While *CodeMeta* already fulfills a lot of different requirements for research software metadata from different use cases in the NFDI consortia, it also has some limitations. For example, *CodeMeta* merges two distinct types from *schema.org* (but does not define the merge as a new type) and self-defined elements of *CodeMeta* are so far not part of an ontology, making it difficult to integrate it into semantic-web-based applications. Also, *CodeMeta* does not recommend nor make certain elements mandatory (or recommended), which would be necessary to ensure a certain quality standard for research software described with such metadata. The elements of *CodeMeta* are not detailed enough to describe the purpose of the software, its interface definition (input, output), its maturity (e.g., prototype), its type (command-line, library, script), its quality, its sustainability⁶, and its connection to research data. In addition, *CodeMeta* does not recommend value vocabularies for certain elements, e.g., for programming languages, operating systems, etc., which would improve the interoperability and semantic usability of the resulting metadata a lot.

¹ M. Gruenpeter et al., “Defining Research Software: a controversial discussion,” Zenodo, Sept. 2021. doi: [10.5281/zenodo.5504016](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5504016).

² M. Barker et al., “Introducing the FAIR Principles for research software,” *Sci Data*, vol. 9, no. 1, Art. no. 1, Oct. 2022, doi: [10.1038/s41597-022-01710-x](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01710-x).

³ A.-L. Lamprecht et al., “Towards FAIR principles for research software,” *Data Science*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 37–59, Jan. 2020, doi: [10.3233/DS-190026](https://doi.org/10.3233/DS-190026).

⁴ M. B. Jones et al., *CodeMeta: an exchange schema for software metadata*. Version 3.0., 2023. Accessed: June 22, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://codemeta.github.io/terms/>

⁵ Guha RV, Brickley D, Macbeth S. *Schema.org: evolution of structured data on the web*. Commun ACM. 2016;59: 44–51. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1145/2844544>

⁶ D. Wilkinson, L. Oliveira, D. Mossé, and B. Childers, “Evaluating Interactive Archives,” 2017. Accessed: Jul. 18, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Evaluating-Interactive-Archives-Wilkinson-Oliveira/e9ad6276399e9e59ce4984193b6f0ae64413919a>

2. Objectives

The overall goal of the working group is to provide a common metadata vocabulary for research software that can be used to develop application profiles to describe research software in the different research domains of the NFDI consortia. The solution should be compatible with common existing semantic frameworks including *schema.org* and metadata already in use in NFDI consortia, and take into account established recommendations such as *CodeMeta*. To reach this goal, the following sub-objectives should be met:

1. Collect different use cases of research software metadata from the different consortia
2. Review existing terminologies for describing (research) software (using *CodeMeta* as reference point) with regard to their suitability for the collected use cases and their adoption by existing software tools and platforms.
3. Define a metadata vocabulary for describing research software reusing existing vocabularies where possible to ensure semantic interoperability, ideally as a *CodeMeta* extension, where new metadata elements are added where needed.
4. Define best practices to use and adopt the vocabulary based on the needs of communities, including recommendations for value vocabularies and mandatory elements.
5. Coordinate adoption of research software metadata in research software directories/catalogs in cooperation with the working group [Research Software in section Infra](#) and the base services [nfdi.software](#).

3. First Outcomes

In the last two years, the WG has already achieved first results. To gain an overview of research software metadata schemas already in use in the different consortia, the WG conducted a survey on the implementation of research software metadata in the NFDI consortia⁷. It was found that only a few domain-specific metadata schemas for research software were in use by different consortia. In contrast, generic metadata schemas such as *CodeMeta*, *Bioschemas*⁸, *schema.org*, and the *CFF*⁹ were most frequently used to describe research software. Relevant metadata elements for research software include algorithms, methods, software/hardware requirements, and tasks performed by the software.

⁷ L. J. Castro et al., “Results on a Survey on Research Software Metadata in the NFDI Consortia,” Zenodo, Aug. 2024. doi: [10.5281/zenodo.12704414](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12704414).

⁸ Gray AJG, Goble C, Jimenez RC. Bioschemas: From Potato Salad to Protein Annotation. ISWC Posters and Demo session. Vienna, Austria; 2017. p. 4. Available: <http://ceur-ws.org/Vol-1963/paper579.pdf>

⁹ Druskat S. Citation File Format (CFF). In: Citation File Format (CFF) [Internet]. 2023 [cited 10 Jul 2024]. Available: <https://citation-file-format.github.io/>

4. Work Plan: Projected timeframes and milestones

The following work plan only lists work packages which are still open. The results of the finalized work packages were presented in the third section.

WP2: Mapping of Existing Terminologies to *CodeMeta* (Q2 2025 - Q1 2026)

- Review literature on different metadata schemes, ontologies, and terminologies to describe research software metadata
- Map the different terminologies to *CodeMeta* and create Crosswalks
- Involved: Stephan Ferez, Leyla Jael Castro, and more

WP3: Define Additional Relevant Metadata Elements (Q1 2026 - Q3 2026)

- Define a list of additional required metadata elements to describe research software based on the results of WP2
- Either add these elements to *CodeMeta* or create an extension to *CodeMeta*
- Involved: Stephan Ferez, Leyla Jael Castro, Aida Jafarbigloo

WP4: Define Recommendations to Use Research Software Metadata in the NFDI (Q3 2026 - Q1 2027)

- Provide recommendations on how to adopt the defined metadata vocabulary in the NFDI consortia
- Gather best practices on software to use the research software metadata
- Involved: Leyla Jael Castro, Stephan Ferez

WP5: Coordinate adoption and adaptation (Q3 2026 - Q4 2027)

- Get feedback from the consortia on the defined metadata vocabulary
- Assist the consortia in applying the metadata vocabulary together with nfdi.software
- Support the consortia to develop domain-specific extensions
- Involved: Leyla Jael Castro, Stephan Ferez

5. Membership List

(At least 6 members from different institutions and at least 6 consortia)

	Name	Institution	NFDI consortia
1	Stephan Ferez (co-spoke)	Universität Oldenburg	NFDI4Energy
2	Oliver Karras	TIB	NFDI4Ing
3	Dorothea Iglezakis	Universität Stuttgart	NFDI4Ing, MaRDI
4	Marc Fuhrmans	TU Darmstadt	NFDI4Ing
5	Jan Göpfert	FZ Jülich	NFDI4Ing
6	Leyla Jael Castro (co-spoke)	ZB Med	NFDI4DS
7	Christian Schmidt-Sonntag	Universität Bielefeld	PUNCH4NFDI
8	Olaf Kaczmarek	Universität Bielefeld	PUNCH4NFDI
9	Matthias Löbe	Universität Leipzig	NFDI4Health

10	Lars Kastner	TU Berlin	MaRDI
11	Luca Ghiringhelli	HU Berlin	FAIRmat
12	Andreas Czerniak	Universität Bielefeld	
13	Alexander Struck	HU Berlin	ExC MoA
14	Patrick Kuckertz	FZ Jülich	NFDI4Ing
15	Ulrik Stervbo	RUB	NFDI4Immuno
16	Frank Löffler	Universität Jena, de-RSE e.V.	
17	Aida Jafarbigloo	Universität Oldenburg/OFFIS	NFDI4Energy
18	Camilla Lüttgens	RWTH Aachen University	
19	Lu Gan	GESIS Leibniz Institute for Social Sciences	
20	Hamideh Hajiabadi	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	NFDIxCs

6. Adoption Plan

Metadata for research software is needed by all consortia that deal with research software, either as a research outcome or as a means of research. Furthermore, it is also needed to develop and consume registries or repositories for research software. With our WP1, we will directly collect requirements from the consortia. Later on, with WP5, we will assist all consortia in applying our metadata vocabulary.

Represented Consortia

NFDI4Ing
NFDI4Energy
MaRDI
NFDI4DS
NFDI4Health
PUNCH4NFDI
FAIRmat

Connected to other NFDI working groups and Base Services

- [WG RSE in Common Infrastructure](#)
- [nfdi.software](#)
- DMP4NFDI via the integration of Software Management Plans

Related projects and approaches within the NFDI

- [Metadata schema for Software Management Plans](#) (ZB MED, NFDI4DS, ELIXIR Software Best Practices Group)
- [DataDesc](#) (NFDI4Ing)

Related projects and approaches outside NFDI

- FAIRCORE4EOSC (also responsible for CodeMeta Governance)
 - Work Package 6 Research Software
- FAIR-IMPACT:
 - D4.4 - Guidelines for recommended metadata standard for research software within EOSC
 - D5.2 - Metrics for automated FAIR software assessment in a disciplinary context
- Software Citation Implementation Working Group
- FAIR for Research Software (FAIR4RS) WG of RDA
- SciCodes: <https://scicodes.net/>
- SoMeSci
- ConnOSS (DFG-funded)
- FutuRSI: a joint initiative supported to conceptualise a German research software institution
- DiscoRSE: working on metadata on open educational resources (OERs) in the field of RSEing

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